

CONCLUDING CONFERENCE FOR
OPEN ACCESS MONITOR - DK

Collection, documentation and administration of
Open Access publication costs in Denmark

A DEFF funded project 2017-2018

Deff

Danmarks Elektroniske
Fag- og Forskningsbibliotek

Time: December 6, 2018 from 10:00-15:00

Place: Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Lecture Hall
(Aud. A 1-01.01), Bülowsvej 17, Frederiksberg C

See [map](#)

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- 9:30-10:00: Registration and coffee
- 10:00-10:10
Welcome by Kira Stine Hansen, Deputy Director, Royal Danish Library | Copenhagen University Library & lead-in by Michael Svendsen, project lead OAM-DK, Royal Danish Library | Copenhagen University Library

1. Part: Data evidence and recommendations for national strategies

- 10:10-10:40
Keynote from Sweden: *Monitoring OA in Sweden and implications of the OA policy roadmap*
Camilla Hertel Lindelöw, National Library of Sweden ([Info](#))
- 10:40-11:30
Keynote from Denmark: *Open Access Monitor - DK: Collection, documentation and administration of OA publishing costs in Denmark – results & recommendations*

Main results:
Monitoring of national OA ecology & economy
Michael Svendsen, Royal Danish Library | Copenhagen University Library & Annette Schneider, Technical University of Denmark
Identification and development of best practice for APC administration in Denmark
Anne Thorst Melbye, University of Southern Denmark & Anna Mette Morthorst, Royal Danish Library | Aarhus University Library
- 11:30-12:00
Keynote from the UK: *Monitoring the transition to OA in the UK*
Rob Johnson, Research Consulting Ltd. ([Report](#))
- 12:00-12:45: Lunch break

2. Part: State of affairs for Open Access in Denmark and Europe

- 12:45-13:15
Review feed back on OAM-DK preliminary report
Jan Erik Frantsovåg, UiT, Norway & Beate Eellend, National Library of Sweden
- 13:15-13:45
Green OA in practice - results and recommendation from DEFF-funded project ([Info](#))
Ane Sand & Anette Schneider, Technical University of Denmark
- 13:45-14:15
[The new Danish Open Access strategy](#)
Hanne-Louise Kierkegaard, Special Adviser, The Ministry of Higher Education & Science
- 14:15-14:50
Panel discussion:
Jan Erik Frantsovåg (NO), Rob Johnson (UK),
Beate Eellend (SE), University or University Library representative - TBC
- 14:50-15:00: Closure by Anne Sandfær, Head of Department for Information Resources, Royal Danish Library | Copenhagen University Library
- 15:00-15:30: Refreshments (Main hall)

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Abstract

Open Access Monitor project (OAM-DK)

In a changing landscape of new Open Access modes, Denmark has adopted a so-called “green” strategy, according to which publication must be kept largely free of charge and publications must be archived in institutional repositories.

Even so, Danish universities spend significant financial resources on Open Access publishing. Substantial fees are being paid to publish via the “golden route” in born-open journals, but also in subscription-based journals via the hybrid model. The latter is especially interesting considering the practice of double-dipping, where universities not only pay for the right-to-read (via the national e-license portfolios) but also for the right-to-publish (via publication fees).

This raises the question of the scale of resources spent on Open Access publishing by Danish universities. This DEFF project follows similar efforts in the UK, Sweden, Norway, Germany and the Netherlands, monitoring how much is being spent on golden and hybrid publishing by Danish universities. The approach has been to identify the publishing ecology of Open Access and derived financial costs. Since it is difficult to gather invoice data, an economic model has been developed to estimate the total cost of publication at Danish universities.

Results show that expenses related to Open Access publishing in the Danish universities are increasing substantially and that monitoring efforts are required.

Executive summary will be sent to attendees November 22

Full report will be available December 21

Read more about the project [here](#)

The participating institutions would like to thank

[DEFF: Denmark's Electronic Research Library](#) for financial support

Keynotes

Camilla Hertil Lindelöw (SE): Consultant at [The National Library of Sweden](#) and part of the Team for Open Access & Licenses, which works to coordinate the national [BIBSAM consortia](#) with Open Access & the portfolio of licenses. Camilla Lindelöw is a specialist in Open Access publishing and various kinds of bibliometric analyses.

Rob Johnson (UK): Founder and director of [Research Consulting](#), which works to improve the effectiveness and impact of research and scholarly communication. Before founding the firm in 2013, Rob came from a position as Head of Research Operations at the University of Nottingham.

Review

Jan Erik Frantsvåg (NO): Senior Adviser at UiT (The Arctic University of Norway) with many years of experience in the field of Open Access. Besides being a chairman of the board of [Sparc Europe](#), member of the [DOAJ](#) advisory board, Jan Erik also organizes the international Open Access conference, [MUNIN](#).

Beate Eellend (SE): PhD, Open Access Programme manager (National Library of Sweden). Beate has a research background in anthropology, and has worked at the [Scientific Council of Formas](#). She is in the board of SPARC Europe and represents [OpenAIRE](#) as the National Open Access Desk for Sweden and as the national point of contact for the [OA2020 initiative](#).

Panel

Jan Erik Frantsvåg (NO)

Rob Johnson (UK)

Beate Eellend (SE)

University or University Library representative - TBC